

NDAC/LO/012

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Further Tests of the IDT Preprocessing Algorithms

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I. PREPROCESSING VS. DIRECT SOLUTION

I-1. Introduction

In NDAC/LO/004 we reported a limited test of the preprocessing algorithm giving the signal parameters $b_1 - b_5$ (NDAC Proposal, Annex A, pp. 27 - 29). We report here some further results of these tests, showing the general feasibility of the preprocessing.

The formulae in NDAC/LO/004 were used unaltered, but with the following updated input data (MATRA E21-HIP-00767 and -00676):

grid period	s	=	1.2	as
scanning speed	v	=	180	as/s
modulation coefficients	M_1	=	0.626	
	M_2	=	0.300	
background count rate	B	=	100	Hz

Each experiment simulated a 2 sec "frame", with the star observed in 10 equidistant time windows of chosen length (= "time fraction" times 0.2 s). Normally, 50 or 100 experiments were done for each selection of star brightness and observing time, and the phase parameters defined in NDAC/LO/004 were computed.

I-2. Results

The mean phases ($\bar{p}_\cdot$, where $\cdot = A, B, C$ for the unconstrained fit, directly constrained fit, and constrained via compressed data) were consistently close to the expected zero value ($\sim 1\sigma$ deviations). The interesting quantities are the rms errors ($p_{\cdot,rms}$). As will be seen below, they do not deviate much from the theor-

etical expectations. As an overview of the expected accuracies, Table I-1 gives the ratios of the phase error to the statistical error $N_{\text{ph}}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, where N_{ph} is the number of stellar photons detected in a 2 sec frame.

Table I-1. Expected phase error (mas) for the unconstrained solution (A) as function of the number of stellar photons detected

N_{ph}	$\approx$ mag	time fraction	σ_A	$\sigma_A N_{\text{ph}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$
160,000	4.0	0.2	0.97 mas	390 mas
10,000	7.0	0.2	3.93	393
962	10.0	0.3	13.1	406
240	12.3	0.6	32.2	497
120	13.0	0.6	53.4	586

As expected, $\sigma_A N_{\text{ph}}^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is approximately constant, with the degradation factor for faint stars about equal to $[1 + B/(I_0 + B)]$.

As already mentioned, the average mean errors ($\bar{\sigma}_i$) are close to their theoretical expectations (Cramér-Rao bound), and these latter are used below, called σ_i . Table I-2 summarizes the experiments performed. Here are given the observed rms values (with estimated error = $p_{\text{rms}}/\sqrt{2N}$) as compared with the expected σ_i -values. The three columns are for the three different solution procedures: A (unconstrained), B (directly constrained), C (constrained via unconstrained).

As can be seen, the observed unconstrained rms values (p_{Arms}) are in excellent agreement with the theoretical expectations. For the constrained solutions, the observed rms is consistently above the expectation by 5-20 %, but as judged by the expected errors in p_{rms} , the increase is barely significant.

Table I-2. Observed rms errors (p_{rms}) compared with Cramér-Rao bounds (σ) for the three solution procedures A, B, C. I_0 = average stellar count rate (Hz), N = number of experiments, ρ_{BC} = correlation between solutions B and C. All errors in mas.

I_0	time frac.	N	P_{Arms}	(σ_A)	P_{Brms}	(σ_B)	P_{Crms}	(σ_C)	ρ_{BC}
400,000	0.2	50	0.94 ± 0.09	(0.97)	0.88 ± 0.09	(0.82)	0.88 ± 0.09	(0.82)	1.0000
25,000	0.2	50	3.78 ± 0.38	(3.93)	3.50 ± 0.35	(3.28)	3.50 ± 0.35	(3.28)	0.9999
4,809	0.1	50	12.2 ± 1.2	(12.8)	11.8 ± 1.2	(10.7)	11.7 ± 1.2	(10.7)	0.999 ± 0.001
1,603	0.3	250	13.0 ± 0.6	(13.1)	11.5 ± 0.6	(10.9)	11.5 ± 0.6	(10.9)	0.998 ± 0.001
1,200	0.1	50	28.4 ± 2.8	(26.6)	26.8 ± 2.7	(22.0)	26.2 ± 2.6	(22.0)	0.990 ± 0.003
400	0.3	100	30.9 ± 2.2	(28.9)	26.8 ± 1.9	(23.7)	27.1 ± 1.9	(23.7)	0.985 ± 0.003
200	0.6	50	31.8 ± 3.2	(32.2)	25.8 ± 2.6	(25.9)	26.2 ± 2.6	(25.9)	0.985 ± 0.004
500	0.2	50	30.3 ± 3.0	(30.9)	28.2 ± 2.8	(25.4)	27.8 ± 2.8	(25.4)	0.988 ± 0.003
200	0.4	50	40.1 ± 4.0	(39.4)	36.5 ± 3.7	(31.7)	36.8 ± 3.7	(31.7)	0.94 ± 0.02
600	0.1	50	38.1 ± 3.8	(39.3)	36.0 ± 3.6	(32.4)	35.0 ± 3.5	(32.4)	0.982 ± 0.005
300	0.2	50	42.4 ± 4.2	(42.5)	36.7 ± 3.7	(34.5)	38.3 ± 3.8	(34.5)	0.85 ± 0.04
200	0.3	50	48.5 ± 4.8	(45.5)	42.9 ± 4.3	(36.6)	44.2 ± 4.4	(36.6)	0.96 ± 0.01
150	0.4	50	49.8 ± 5.0	(48.3)	39.8 ± 4.0	(38.4)	46.2 ± 4.6	(38.4)	0.86 ± 0.04
100	0.6	50	55.9 ± 5.6	(53.4)	44.0 ± 4.4	(41.9)	47.6 ± 4.8	(41.9)	0.97 ± 0.01
100	0.5	50	63.5 ± 6.3	(58.5)	48.2 ± 4.8	(45.9)	54.9 ± 5.5	(45.9)	0.90 ± 0.03

The interesting question to be answered by these experiments is mainly if there is any difference between the B and C solutions, i.e. if going via the unconstrained solution (data compression) in any way degrades the results. In the last column of Table I-2 is given the correlation coefficient between the estimation errors of the two procedures. For bright stars ($m < 10$), the correlation is virtually perfect, but with decreasing brightness there are deviations: The observed correlation shows rather great fluctuations, being mostly due to a few very large B - C differences. (With fewer than about 100 observed photons, we had problems using the C-solution as a start for the B-iterations. When these differed greatly, the B-solution simply did not converge.) The increase in $p_{C \text{ rms}}$ as compared to $p_{B \text{ rms}}$ is significant only for the very faintest stars.

I-3. Conclusions

From the above experiments it seems safe to conclude that the large deviations between raw data solutions vs. solution with preprocessing reported by the FAST Consortium (FAST Proposal, Technical Annex 3.1) must be largely spurious. Our results show a slight degrading for the faintest observable stars ($m \approx 13$), but even there the effect is less than 15 %. For the large majority of HIPPARCOS stars, the results after preprocessing are indistinguishable from raw data solutions.

II. LOCATION ESTIMATOR

II-1. Introduction

In NDAC/LO/010 is given the method proposed for improving the original ($\hat{\beta}$) signal parameters using information from the OTF data file. If the star is single, observed estimates $\tilde{\beta}_4$ and $\tilde{\beta}_5$ are available, and an improved β^* can be calculated. For a faint star, this is nearly equivalent to a rigorous constraint, while for bright stars no improvement may be possible. For a binary or multiple star, the observed signal parameters may show significant deviations as compared to the single-star calibration, and the location estimation is one step in the process of double-star recognition. This note reports some trial calculations that illustrate the principles involved.

II-2. Calculations and results

The instrumental parameters and "observation" principles are as for the preprocessing calculations reported in Part I above. For the covariance of $\tilde{\beta}_4$ and $\tilde{\beta}_5$ we use simply

$$\underline{G} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{\text{cal}}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{\text{cal}}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

with σ_{cal} a free parameter. As an illustration of the rôle of σ_{cal} , Table II-1 gives the theoretical (Cramér-Rao) mean errors for the "standard" case $I_0 = 1603$ Hz, time fraction = 0.3. As expected, a large σ_{cal} gives the unconstrained solution, while a small σ_{cal} acts like a rigorous constraint.

Table II-1. Theoretical mean errors as function of σ_{cal}

σ_{cal}	$\sigma(\beta_1^*)$	$\sigma(\beta_2^*)$	$\sigma(\beta_3^*)$	$\sigma(\beta_4^*)$	$\sigma(\beta_5^*)$
∞	.0444	.0665	.0686	.0720	.0821
1	.0444	.0665	.0686	.0718	.0818
0.1	.0444	.0656	.0642	.0584	.0634
0.01	.0444	.0641	.0573	.0099	.0099
0.001	.0444	.0640	.0571	.0010	.0010
0	.0444	.0640	.0571	.0000	.0000

As before, we are mainly interested in the error p_{rms} for the phase parameter β_3^* . Table II-2 shows the results of some simulations with σ_{cal} fixed at 0.01. The C-solution is the "constrained from unconstrained" of Part I, while D stands for the present "partially constrained". As seen from the column ρ_{CD} , the correlation between these two solutions is very high as soon as $\sigma(\hat{\beta}_4)/\sigma_{\text{cal}} \gg 1$. The trend with $p_{\text{rms}} > \sigma$ for faint stars is also apparent.

Also given in Table II-2 are the two first moments of the y -distribution, y being the goodness-of-fit parameter defined in NDAC/LO/010. It is stated there that in the limiting case when $\sigma_{\text{cal}} \ll \sigma(\hat{\beta}_{4,5})$, we would expect y to follow a χ^2 -distribution with 2 degrees of freedom. Actually, however, with the definition given it is $2y$ that should follow this distribution, which means we should expect $\langle y \rangle = 1$, $\langle y^2 \rangle = 2$. This expectation is fulfilled for most of the trials in Table II-2. (The detailed statistics also conform to the χ^2 -distribution.) In the bright star end, the distribution gets narrower as expected, but for the faintest stars a similar trend is more difficult to explain. The effect must be somehow due to the low photon counts that make the asymptotic properties of maximum likelihood estimates inapplicable.

A similar faint-star bias is shown by the β_2^* parameter, which is systematically overestimated in the D-solution as shown in Table II-3.

II-3. Conclusions

For most purposes, the "partially constrained" solution (D) obtained via the observed G -matrix gives meaningful improved estimates for the signal parameters. For faint stars, there are some problems with β_2^* , but the phase estimate β_3^* is unbiased and close to the expected constrained solution.

The y -distributions are mostly close to a scaled χ^2 -distribution with 2 degrees of freedom. That is, we may define a factor $f_y(I_0, \sigma_{\text{cal}}/\sigma_{\hat{\beta}}, \dots)$ such that the single-star hypothesis is rejected whenever $f_y > \chi_{\text{lim}}^2$. The adopted formula for

Table II-2. Observed rms errors (in mas) for the solution procedures C and D

I_0	time frac	N	approx mag	$\frac{\sigma(\beta_4)}{\sigma_{cal}}$	$P_{C rms}$	(σ_C)	$P_{D rms}$	(σ_D)	ρ_{CD}	$\langle y \rangle$	$\langle y^2 \rangle$
1,000,000	0.1	100	3.0	0.5	0.78	(0.73)	0.86	(0.84)	0.879	0.05	0.00
100,000	0.1	100	5.5	1.5	2.50	(2.31)	2.52	(2.44)	0.988	0.49	0.51
10,000	0.1	100	8.0	5	6.78	(7.37)	6.76	(7.41)	0.9997	0.97	2.00
1,603	0.3	100	10.0	7	11.80	(10.90)	11.78	(10.94)	0.9999	0.96	2.18
800	0.3	100	10.8	11	17.21	(15.89)	17.21	(15.91)	0.9996	1.01	2.24
400	0.3	100	11.5	16	24.37	(23.66)	24.43	(23.68)	0.9992	0.97	1.98
200	0.3	100	12.2	25	42.23	(36.55)	42.15	(36.57)	0.9992	0.90	1.45
150	0.4	50	12.6	27	42.48	(38.45)	42.75	(38.46)	0.9993	0.67	1.02
100	0.6	50	13.0	30	47.56	(41.94)	48.07	(41.94)	0.9993	0.55	0.58
100	0.5	50	13.0	33	70.82	(45.93)	70.40	(45.95)	0.9992	0.70	0.99
80	0.6	50	13.2	36	56.49	(49.58)	56.97	(49.58)	0.9992	0.61	0.71

f_y is not critical, but it should be based on more extensive simulations than the present runs. As a rough guide one may use

$$f_y = \begin{cases} 10[\sigma_{\text{cal}}/\sigma(\hat{\beta}_4)]^2 & \text{for } \sigma_{\text{cal}}/\sigma(\hat{\beta}_4) \gtrsim 0.5 \\ 2 + (B/I_0)^2 & \text{for } \sigma_{\text{cal}}/\sigma(\hat{\beta}_4) \lesssim 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Table II-3. Observed mean β_2 -values for solution procedures C (constrained from unconstrained) and D (partially constrained)

I_0	time frac	N	$\beta_{2,\text{true}}$	$\langle\beta_{2,C}\rangle$	$\langle\beta_{2,D}\rangle$
1,000,000	0.1	100	521.7	522.1 ± 0.3	522.1 ± 0.3
100,000	0.1	100	52.17	52.33 ± 0.09	52.34 ± 0.09
10,000	0.1	100	5.22	5.22 ± 0.03	5.25 ± 0.03
1,603	0.3	100	0.836	0.839 ± 0.008	0.848 ± 0.008
800	0.3	100	0.417	0.426 ± 0.005	0.435 ± 0.005
400	0.3	100	0.209	0.216 ± 0.004	0.226 ± 0.004
200	0.3	100	0.104	0.108 ± 0.003	0.120 ± 0.003
150	0.4	50	0.078	0.083 ± 0.003	0.090 ± 0.003
100	0.6	50	0.052	0.055 ± 0.002	0.060 ± 0.002
100	0.5	50	0.052	0.057 ± 0.003	0.064 ± 0.003
80	0.6	50	0.042	0.046 ± 0.002	0.051 ± 0.002

III. INFLUENCE OF REFERENCE PHASE ERRORS

III-1. Introduction

In the investigations reported in Parts I and II of this note, the reference modulation phases (H_k) were assumed to be exactly known. In practice, one must expect also some speed errors and/or accelerations that will affect the signal parameter estimation. Here we describe some preliminary studies of these effects. Further simulations with more realistic attitude motions will be required.

III-2. Phase error model

For simplicity, the reference phase errors were given by the expression *)

$$\Delta H = (h_1 t + h_2 t^2) (2\pi/s) \quad (3)$$

with h_1 and h_2 in as/s and as/s^2 . The "true" mean phase over ten intervals of $F/5$ seconds duration (starting at $t = 0$) then corresponds to the image displacement

$$\Delta \eta_0 = \frac{9+F}{10} h_1 + \frac{171+27F+2F^2}{150} h_2 \quad (4)$$

(In order for the observations of different stars in one frame to be "quasi-simultaneous", a more symmetrical arrangement may be preferred, see Section 5 below.)

III-3. Non-randomized simulations

In Parts I and II of this note, we studied the deviations between "observed" and "true" signal parameters due to photon noise. When the reference phases are in error, even an "exact" solution (with non-randomized photon numbers) is biased, and we study first these errors. Table III-1 shows the deviations between the partially constrained D-solution ($\sigma_{cal} = 0.01$; see Part II) and the true phases given by Eqn (4) for a number of (h_1, h_2)-combinations and a number of I_0 -values. The time fraction is $F = 0.3$.

*) Note that the actual acceleration is $2h_2$.

Table III-1. Phase deviations $\Delta\eta_{\text{obs}} - \Delta\eta_0$ in mas.

Solution	I_0	$h_1 =$	.00	.06	.12	.00	.06	.12	.00	.06	.12
		$h_2 =$	.00	.00	.00	.03	.03	.03	.06	.06	.06
A	-		0.0	-0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.5	-1.3	-0.9	-2.4	-4.6
C	-		0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3	-1.3	-3.3	-2.3	-6.0	-12.1
D	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 10^6 \\ 10^5 \\ 10^4 \\ 1603 \\ 200 \end{array} \right.$		0.0	-0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.6	-1.5	-1.1	-2.7	-5.5
			0.0	-0.0	-0.0	-0.2	-0.9	-2.4	-1.6	-4.3	-9.1
			0.0	-0.1	+0.0	-0.3	-1.2	-3.2	-2.2	-5.8	-12.0
			0.0	-0.0	+0.0	-0.3	-1.2	-3.3	-2.3	-6.1	-12.5
			0.0	-0.0	-0.1	-0.3	-1.3	-3.4	-2.4	-6.3	-12.8
A-C	-		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.8	2.0	1.4	3.6	7.5

Also shown is the unconstrained (A) and the fully constrained (C) solutions. (The A-solution is totally independent of I_0 , the C-solution almost so.) Because these two are different, the D-solution with a variable degree of constraint shows a non-negligible "magnitude equation". The last line of Table III-1 gives the difference between the A and C solutions, which is also about the maximum amplitude for the magnitude effects. Roughly, these figures are reproduced by the expression

$$|A-C| = 5000 h_2^2 (h_2 + 2.9h_1) \quad [\text{mas}] \quad (5)$$

For reasonable values of h_1 ($\lesssim 0.05$ as/s), one must then have $h_2 \lesssim 0.01$ as/s² in order to have $|A-C| < 0.1$ mas.

Another effect that can be studied in these simulations is the increase of the expected mean errors of the phase determinations with h_1 and h_2 . This effect is nearly independent of I_0 and F , and it is closely modelled by the quadratic expression

$$\sigma(h_1, h_2) = \sigma(0, 0) \left[1 + 1.4(h_1 + 2h_2)^2 \right] \quad (6)$$

With $h_1 < 0.05$ as/s and $h_2 < 0.01$ as/s², the increase in σ is less than 1 %.

III-4. Monte-Carlo simulations

The effects studied in Section 3 are further aggravated by the random errors. Table III-2 gives results for simulations with rather large (h_1, h_2) -values in order for the deviations to stand out clearly.

Table III-2. Simulated phase determinations for the partially constrained D-solution ($\sigma_{\text{cal}} = 0.01$) for $h_1 = 0.06$ as/s, $h_2 = 0.03$ as/s².

I_0	F	N	$\bar{P}_D - \Delta\eta_0$	$P_{D \text{ rms}}$	(σ_D)	$\langle y \rangle$	$\langle y^2 \rangle$
1,000,000	0.3	25	-0.5 ± 0.1	0.59 ± 0.08	(0.55)	2.66	7.08
1,000,000	0.1	25	-0.7 ± 0.2	0.97 ± 0.14	(0.94)	5.73	33.30
100,000	0.3	50	-0.7 ± 0.2	1.74 ± 0.17	(1.66)	9.33	90.08
100,000	0.1	100	-0.8 ± 0.3	2.75 ± 0.19	(2.79)	8.01	72.03
10,000	0.3	25	-3.0 ± 0.9	4.6 ± 0.6	(5.0)	3.84	18.68
10,000	0.1	25	-3.2 ± 1.2	6.1 ± 0.9	(8.6)	2.37	8.40
1,603	0.3	150	-2.7 ± 0.9	11.4 ± 0.7	(12.8)	1.67	5.18
200	0.3	100	-5.7 ± 4.5	45 ± 3	(42)	0.87	1.53

Comparison with Table III-1 reveals at once that the phase errors are now significantly greater for the fainter stars, giving a large "magnitude equation". The mean errors are at or below their expectations, but the y-values (see Part II) show a remarkable increase. This is shown more clearly in Table III-3, which indicates, however, that accelerations below $h_2 = 0.01 - 0.02$ as/s² are rather harmless in this respect.

Table III-3. Mean y-values for some combinations of h_1, h_2, I_0, F

I_0	F	$h_1 = 0.00$	0.02	0.04	0.06
		$h_2 = 0.00$	0.01	0.02	0.03
1,000,000	0.1	0.05	0.11	1.16	5.73
100,000	0.1	0.49	0.53	1.93	8.01
10,000	0.1	0.97	1.22	1.51	2.37
1,603	0.3	0.96		1.06	1.67

III-5. Effects of non-simultaneity

The above simulations are still for the case of ideally simultaneous observations. In reality, any observing strategy will give different time distributions of the observations for different stars. Clearly, the 'Regular Cyclic Observing Strategy' (Fig. 1) is quite sensitive to speed errors, since the actual mean epochs for the different stars may differ by up to about 0.2 s (with the assumptions in Part I). This could be avoided with a symmetric scheme as in Figure 2. The mean epoch is then the same for all stars, but in the presence of an acceleration, the mean phases are still different. If a star is observed from fraction f_1 to fraction f_2 in each of the n observation intervals before the middle of the frame ($n = 5$ in Fig. 2), and from fraction $1-f_2$ to $1-f_1$ in each of the n intervals after the middle, the mean phase due to the $h_2 t^2$ -term in (3) is found to produce the displacement

$$\delta\eta = \frac{h_2 T_4^2}{24n^2} \left[1 + 3n + 8n^2 - 3(n+1)(f_1 + f_2) + 2(f_1^2 + f_1 f_2 + f_2^2) \right] \quad (7)$$

with $T_4 = 2$ s being the frame interval. The phase difference between a star observed from $f_1 = 0$ to $f_2 = F$ and one observed from $f_1 = 1-F$ to $f_2 = 1$ turns out to be simply

$$\Delta(\delta\eta) = (1-F) h_2 T_4^2 / (4n) \quad (8)$$

For a typical $F = 0.3$, $n = 5$, we find $\Delta(\delta\eta) = 1.4$ mas for $h_2 = 0.01$ as/s². The non-simultaneity will thus impose more stringent limits on h_2 than the "magnitude effects" of Sections 3 and 4.

III-6. Conclusions

It is seen that acceleration errors of the attitude used for the image location are troublesome in several respects. Their most important effect is a magnitude equation of at least twice the size given by Eqn (5). Also, the observing strategy has to be optimized in order that the observations of different stars in a frame can be assumed to be simultaneous. Alternatively, phase corrections may be applied at a later stage when the attitude motion is more accurately known.

FIGURE 1. Regular Cyclic Observing Strategy (4 stars in a 2^S frame)

FIGURE 2. Symmetricized Regular Cyclic Observing Strategy